

Ultra sound study on Molecular Interaction of binary liquid mixtures of Eugenol with Halobenzenes across variable temperatures

Kulsum Shaikh, Rignesh Patel and Sangita Sharma*

Department of Chemistry, Hemchandracharya North Gujarat University, Patan, Gujarat-384265, India

Abstract: Densities, (ρ) and the speed of sound, (u), for the binary liquid mixtures of Eugenol + Fluoro benzene, Eugenol + Chloro benzene, Eugenol + Bromo benzene, over the whole composition range have been measured at $T = (303.15, 308.15, \text{ and } 313.15) \text{ K}$, and at atmospheric pressure. Experimental data for the densities and speeds of sound have been used to derive the quantities like the excess molar volume (V_m^E), deviation in isentropic compressibility (Δk_s), and Deviation in speed of sound (Δu). These excess parameters were correlated by the Redlich–Kister polynomial function. The results are discussed in terms of molecular interactions and compared with literature data.

Keywords: Density, Speed of sound, Redlich-Kister polynomial equation, excess properties.

Introduction:

The measurement of the speed of sound in liquid mixture enables accurate determination of some useful acoustical parameters and their excess values, which are highly sensitive to molecular interactions in their mixtures [1-5]. Eugenol is the major component of several essential oils such as cinnamon leaf oil and clove leaf oil, and, due to its high availability in natural sources, it is preferably isolated from clove oil [6]. The demand for essential clove oil distilled from flower bud (bud oil), flower stalks (stem oil), and leaves (leaf oil), is very high on the market. It is used in field's pharmacology, agriculture, food industry, cosmetics and various other industries [7-9]. The production of essential clove oil in Indonesia is only limited to cultivated cloves, for it is considered to be of good quality with high eugenol level, about 70-90% [10-12]. The main aim of this work is to provide information on the molecular interactions between Eugenol and halo benzenes from the measurements of V_m^E , Δk_s and Δu data so that these data can be used in the future in pharmaceutical applications. The data on excess thermodynamic properties will provide sufficient and useful information on the intermolecular and structural interactions that are prevailing between the components of the mixtures with different shapes, sizes, and chemical nature [13-15]. These interpretation data are useful in explaining the behavior of mixtures and modification in liquid properties, perfumery, etc.

Material and Procedures:

Eugenol (with >98% purity, Himedia Pvt. Ltd., India), fluorobenzene (with 99% purity, S. D. Fine Chem. Ltd., India), chlorobenzene (with 99.5% purity, S. D. Fine Chem. Ltd., India), bromobenzene (with 98% purity, S. D. Fine Chem. Ltd., India) were used in this study as received and used in the current investigation, purities of the solvents are as shown in Table 1. The binary mixtures were prepared by mass using an Electronic balance (Reptech RA-2012) with a precision of $\pm 0.0001 \text{ g}$. The measurement range of weight balance is 210 g to 0.1 mg with an accuracy of $\pm 0.0001 \text{ g}$. The uncertainty in mole fraction was estimated to be ± 0.0001 . The purities of the liquids were checked by comparing the values of densities and viscosity with literature data and are given in Table 2 [16-25]. Samples were placed in a dark place to avoid the photolytic effect.

Table -1 List of Chemicals with Details of Supplier, CAS Number, Purity, Purification Method and Applied Method for Final Purity Analysis

Component	Source	CAS Number	Initial Mass Fraction Purity	Purification Method	Final mass fraction purity	Analysis method
Eugenol	Himedia Pvt. Ltd., India	97-53-0	98%	None	-	-
Fluorobenzene	S. D. Fine Chem. Ltd., India	462-06-6	99%	Fractional distillation	99.9%	GC ^a
chlorobenzene	S. D. Fine Chem. Ltd., India	108-90-7	99.5%	Fractional distillation	99.9%	GC ^a
Bromobenzene	S. D. Fine Chem. Ltd., India	108-86-1	98%	Fractional distillation	99.8%	GC ^a

Density and Speed of Sound Measurements: The densities and speed of the pure liquids and their mixtures were measured with a density and speed of sound analyzer apparatus (Anton Paar, DMA 500M) was used. The U-shaped oscillating tube is first cleaned with methanol, followed by distilled water to ensure thorough cleaning. Afterward, an air pump connected to the instrument is used to dry the pipe with an air stream. Density and sound speed measurements are taken five minutes after the dry air passes through the pipe. To verify the instrument's calibration, the target values for sound speed and density should be 163.77 m/s and 0.00128 g/cm³, respectively. After calibration, the sample is injected through the intake pipe until the solution flows out of the output pipe, with a minimum sample volume of 3 mL required. The U-shaped tube is then cleaned with methanol after each use and allowed to air dry. The density can be measured with an accuracy range of 0 to 3 g/cm³.

The functions of excess molar volume are highly sensitive to intermolecular interactions between the component molecules of the mixture. The values of the functions excess molar volume (V_m^E) were computed using the following relation.

$$V_m^E (\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}) = V_m - V_1 x_1 - V_2 x_2 \quad (1)$$

$$V_m^E (\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}) = \left(\frac{x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2}{\rho_m} \right) - \left(\frac{x_1 M_1}{\rho_1} \right) - \left(\frac{x_2 M_2}{\rho_2} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where, V_1 , V_2 , are molar volume of component 1, and 2 having mole fractions x_1 and x_2 respectively and V_m^E is the excess molar volume mixture. (V_m^E) can be obtained by the measurements of densities of pure components and these of mixtures. M_1 , and M_2 are molecular weight of pure liquids.

The value of deviation in the speed of sound (Δu) were computed using the following relation.

$$\Delta u (\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}) = u_{exp} - (x_1 u_1 + x_2 u_2) \quad (3)$$

Where, u_{exp} denotes speed of sound of binary mixture. x_1, x_2 represents mole fraction and u_1, u_2 represents speed of sound of pure component 1 and 2 respectively.

The values deviation in isentropic compressibility (Δk_s) were calculated using following relations.

$$k_s (\text{T Pa}^{-1}) = \frac{1}{u_f^2 \rho_i} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta k_s = k_{s_{exp}} - (x_1 k_{s_1} + x_2 k_{s_2}) \quad (5)$$

Where, $k_{s_{exp}}$ is isentropic compressibility of mixture having mole fraction x_1 and x_2 of 1 and 2 component respectively k_{s_1} and k_{s_2} are isentropic compressibilities. Δk_s is deviation in isentropic compressibility.

Table-2 Observed and Literature Values of Density (ρ) and Speed of Sound (u) of Pure Components at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 and at atmospheric pressure.

Component	T/K	ρ (gm.cm ³)		u (m.s ⁻¹)	
		observed	literture	observed	literture
Eugenol	303.15	1.057441	1.057638[16]	1458	1460[16]
	308.15	1.053023	1.053211[16]	1439	1276[16]
	313.15	1.048598	1.048784[16]	1422	1282[16]
Fluorobenzene	303.15	1.013104	1.01314[18-19]	1144	1145[17]
	308.15	1.007057	1.007072[17]	1124	1125[17]
	313.15	1.000978	1.000994[17]	1104	1105[17]
Chlorobenzene	303.15	1.095500	1.09510[21]	1248	1249[19]
	308.15	1.090086	1.090400[17]	1230	1231[17]
	313.15	1.084659	1.084974[17]	1212	1212[24]
Bromobenzene	303.15	1.481009	1.4810[20]	1138	1137[22]
	308.15	1.474240	1.47481[19]	1222	1122[23]
	313.15	1.467464	1.467595[17]	1107	1109[25]

Results and discussion:

The measured excess molar volumes, (V_m^E), Deviation in Speed of Sound (Δu) and Deviation in Isentropic Compressibility (Δk_s) as function of mole fraction (x_1) of Eugenol with fluorobenzene, chlorobenzene and bromobenzene at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15K are reported in Table 3, Table 5 and Table 7 and graphically represented as Figures 1, Figures 2 and Figures 3 respectively.

Table-3 Density (ρ) and Excess Molar Volume (V_m^E) vs Mole Fraction (x_1) for Eugenol + Fluoro-, Chloro- and Bromobenzene Mixtures at Different Temperatures

x_1	ρ (g·cm ³)			V_m^E (cm ³ ·mol ⁻¹)		
	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K
Eugenol (1) + Fluorobenzene (2)						
0.0000	1.013104	1.007057	1.000978	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
0.0636	1.018023	1.012012	1.005939	-0.0471	-0.0359	-0.0213
0.1325	1.022899	1.017010	1.011083	-0.0933	-0.0786	-0.0626
0.2075	1.027865	1.022073	1.016224	-0.1525	-0.1314	-0.1065
0.2894	1.032658	1.027052	1.021340	-0.1979	-0.1791	-0.1507
0.3792	1.037322	1.031904	1.026393	-0.2327	-0.2162	-0.1911
0.4782	1.041827	1.036592	1.031324	-0.2519	-0.2370	-0.2200
0.5877	1.046203	1.041118	1.036021	-0.2571	-0.2393	-0.2217
0.7096	1.050379	1.045427	1.040493	-0.2367	-0.2131	-0.1933
0.8461	1.054215	1.049422	1.044633	-0.1672	-0.1401	-0.1146
1.0000	1.057441	1.053023	1.048598	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Eugenol (1) + Chlorobenzene (2)						
0.0000	1.095500	1.090086	1.084659	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
0.0685	1.091398	1.086170	1.080901	0.0289	0.0209	0.0156
0.1419	1.087331	1.082227	1.077141	0.0565	0.0461	0.0325
0.2209	1.083288	1.078302	1.073362	0.0838	0.0715	0.0527
0.3061	1.079286	1.074411	1.069567	0.1090	0.0952	0.0764
0.3982	1.075392	1.070609	1.065848	0.1240	0.1105	0.0930
0.4981	1.071598	1.066918	1.062237	0.1283	0.1137	0.0978
0.6069	1.067892	1.063308	1.058718	0.1219	0.1068	0.0911
0.7258	1.064298	1.059781	1.055311	0.0999	0.0880	0.0684
0.8562	1.060794	1.056382	1.051973	0.0631	0.0491	0.0334
1.0000	1.057441	1.053023	1.048598	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Eugenol (1) + Bromobenzene (2)						
0.0000	1.481009	1.474240	1.467464	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
0.0705	1.437998	1.431788	1.425374	0.0498	0.0265	0.0181

0.1458	1.395214	1.389288	1.383181	0.0877	0.0602	0.0465
0.2264	1.352476	1.346833	1.341024	0.1267	0.0941	0.0749
0.3128	1.309892	1.304493	1.298943	0.1566	0.1215	0.0994
0.4057	1.267454	1.262255	1.257012	0.1761	0.1422	0.1114
0.5060	1.225165	1.220166	1.215172	0.1820	0.1491	0.1143
0.6144	1.182989	1.178186	1.173402	0.1754	0.1437	0.1084
0.7320	1.140963	1.136347	1.131736	0.1484	0.1188	0.0871
0.8600	1.099096	1.094661	1.090124	0.0947	0.0679	0.0536
1.0000	1.057441	1.053023	1.048598	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Standard uncertainties U, in case of density (ρ), $U(T) = \pm 0.001$ K, $U(\rho) = \pm 0.000001$ g·cm³, $U(x_1) = \pm 0.0001$. All physical quantities are measured at atmospheric pressure.

Table-4 Fitting Coefficients (A_0, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4) with Standard Deviation (σ) for Least Square Representation of V_m^E for Eugenol+ Fluoro- + Chloro- + and Bromobenzene Mixtures at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15K.

T (K)	A_0	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	σ
Eugenol (1) + Fluorobenzene (2)						
303.15	-1.028460	-0.177863	-0.102839	-0.260659	0.003349	0.00279
308.15	-0.964610	-0.164551	0.099729	-0.179054	0.053920	0.00161
313.15	-0.880882	-0.240092	0.153279	0.032878	0.364773	0.00176
Eugenol (1) + Chlorobenzene (2)						
303.15	0.518306	-0.020929	-0.111063	0.102253	0.113034	0.00086
308.15	0.458675	-0.008479	-0.092283	0.041910	-0.080464	0.00105
313.15	0.391836	0.003166	-0.326274	-0.005510	0.154625	0.00191
Eugenol (1) + Bromobenzene (2)						
303.15	0.737144	0.030949	-0.058611	0.025685	0.185894	0.00177
308.15	0.597879	0.052023	-0.044204	0.013505	-0.198199	0.00046
313.15	0.460170	-0.038210	-0.026195	0.178662	-0.153733	0.00083

Figure1- Excess molar volume (V_m^E) for the system Eugenol (1) + Fluoro-, Chloro-, and Bromobenzene (2) as a function of mole fraction at $T = 303.15$ K: ■, Eugenol (1) + Fluorobenzene (2); ●, Eugenol (1) + Chlorobenzene (2); ▲, Eugenol (1) + Bromobenzene (2).

The excess molar volume (V_m^E) values for binary mixtures containing fluorobenzene are negative, whereas the values are positive for binary mixtures containing chlorobenzene and bromobenzene. As the temperature increases, the (V_m^E) values increase. The binary mixture of Eugenol and fluorobenzene exhibits the highest negative value of (V_m^E) among all the binary mixtures studied. The negative value of the excess molar volume (V_m^E) indicates strong presence of intermolecular interactions between unlike molecules while a positive value of (V_m^E) indicates the presence of weak attractive or repulsive type interactions between components of binary mixtures [1-5].

In this study, the excess molar volume (V_m^E) values are negative for fluorobenzene and positive for chlorobenzene and bromobenzene in binary mixtures. This suggests that the (V_m^E) value is influenced by two factors.

The first factor involves physical intermolecular forces, which include dispersion forces and repulsion between nonpolar molecules, induction forces between a permanent dipole and an induced dipole, and electrostatic forces between charged particles and permanent dipoles. These forces can result in either positive or negative (V_m^E) values and they are typically weak.

The second factor relates to the structural features of the components, which arise from the geometrical fitting of one component into the structure of the other due to variations in component size, shape, and free volume.

The negative excess molar volume values observed for the binary mixtures of Eugenol with fluorobenzene and positive values for chlorobenzene, and bromobenzene. The apparent intermolecular interactions in the binary mixtures of Eugenol with fluorobenzene, chlorobenzene, or bromobenzene can be classified as strong dipolar-induced forces. These forces may result from the polarization of the halobenzene molecules by the dipoles of the surrounding Eugenol molecules. Among the binary mixtures, a stronger interaction is observed between Eugenol and fluorobenzene than between Eugenol and chlorobenzene or bromobenzene. This is because the fluorine atom is highly electronegative, followed by chlorine and bromine. Therefore, the Eugenol + fluorobenzene binary mixture exhibits the highest negative value of (V_m^E) value indicating that the fluorobenzene molecules are strongly attracted to the Eugenol molecules.

The interaction tendency of Eugenol with Halobenzenes is as follow

Fluorobenzene>Chlorobenzene>Bromobenzene

Table -5 Speed of Sound (u) and Deviation in Speed of Sound (Δu) vs Mole Fraction (x_1) for Eugenol + Fluoro-, Chloro- and Bromobenzene Mixtures at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15K.

x_1	u (m·s ⁻¹)			Δu (m·s ⁻¹)		
	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K
Eugenol (1) + Fluorobenzene (2)						
0.0000	1144.30	1124.12	1103.94	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.0636	1165.89	1146.08	1126.28	1.67	1.96	2.14
0.1325	1189.51	1169.66	1150.13	3.69	3.86	4.09
0.2075	1215.09	1195.46	1175.99	5.76	6.07	6.12
0.2894	1243.17	1223.07	1203.45	8.17	7.91	7.55
0.3792	1272.87	1252.64	1233.11	9.72	9.22	8.67
0.4782	1304.48	1284.24	1264.95	10.32	9.70	9.07
0.5877	1338.31	1318.32	1299.46	9.82	9.32	8.77
0.7096	1374.46	1354.92	1336.63	7.76	7.57	7.21
0.8461	1413.76	1394.68	1377.05	4.28	4.39	4.25
1.0000	1457.71	1438.70	1421.70	0.00	0.00	0.00
Eugenol (1) + Chlorobenzene (2)						
0.0000	1248.35	1230.14	1211.92	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.0685	1264.21	1246.05	1227.34	1.52	1.63	1.05
0.1419	1281.69	1263.12	1244.57	3.62	3.38	2.87
0.2209	1300.17	1281.28	1263.02	5.57	5.06	4.75
0.3061	1320.21	1301.49	1283.08	7.78	7.51	6.95
0.3982	1340.88	1321.80	1303.58	9.16	8.61	8.13
0.4981	1362.01	1342.79	1324.85	9.37	8.76	8.43
0.6069	1384.13	1364.78	1346.75	8.72	8.06	7.51
0.7258	1407.16	1387.65	1369.69	6.86	6.14	5.52
0.8562	1431.29	1411.95	1394.39	3.68	3.24	2.85
1.0000	1457.71	1438.70	1421.70	0.00	0.00	0.00
Eugenol (1) + Bromobenzene (2)						
0.0000	1138.28	1122.03	1106.80	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.0705	1161.70	1145.26	1129.38	0.90	0.90	0.38
0.1458	1187.77	1170.62	1154.67	2.92	2.42	1.96
0.2264	1215.70	1198.14	1181.89	5.11	4.43	3.81
0.3128	1245.06	1227.19	1211.11	6.87	6.11	5.81
0.4057	1275.89	1258.05	1241.66	8.01	7.54	7.10

0.5060	1308.21	1290.09	1273.41	8.31	7.84	7.29
0.6144	1342.15	1323.57	1306.84	7.63	6.99	6.58
0.7320	1377.68	1358.92	1341.86	5.59	5.10	4.56
0.8600	1415.92	1396.81	1379.66	2.92	2.43	2.04
1.0000	1457.71	1438.70	1421.70	0.00	0.00	0.00
Standard uncertainties U, $U(T) = \pm 0.001$ K, $U(x) = \pm 0.0001$, $U(u) = \pm 0.1$ m·s ⁻¹ . All physical quantities are measured at atmospheric pressure.						

Table-6Fitting Coefficients (A_0, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4) with Standard Deviation (σ) for Least Square Representation of Δu for Eugenol + Fluoro-, Chloro- and Bromobenzene Mixtures at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15K.

T (K)	A_0	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	σ
Eugenol(1) + Fluorobenzene (2)						
303.15	41.70510	-2.83464	-20.86490	5.56697	5.82738	0.09689
308.15	39.23170	-2.39063	-11.55960	2.93283	3.35923	0.08146
313.15	36.50690	-1.85948	-3.19197	-1.75019	-1.99569	0.05898
Eugenol (1) + Chlorobenzene (2)						
303.15	37.90250	-2.33327	-15.05320	5.44745	-2.35941	0.11214
308.15	35.91290	-3.87542	-24.69560	5.75025	14.70120	0.20528
313.15	33.77170	-6.10685	-22.61830	11.89640	3.59954	0.07989
Eugenol (1) + Bromobenzene (2)						
303.15	33.15670	-4.32425	-11.67790	10.48820	-14.09070	0.08510
308.15	31.43750	-2.50825	-24.00830	6.03607	2.90780	0.05350
313.15	29.49290	-3.72905	-23.96140	10.20650	-4.78764	0.06399

Figure 2-Deviation in speed of sound (Δu) for the system Eugenol (1) + Fluoro-, Chloro-, and Bromobenzene (2) as a function of mole fraction at $T = 303.15$ K: ■, Eugenol (1) + Fluorobenzene (2); ●, Eugenol (1) + Chlorobenzene (2); ▲, Eugenol (1) + Bromobenzene (2).

Deviation in speed of sound, Δu values for fluorobenzene, chlorobenzene and bromobenzene containing binary mixtures are positive at different selected temperatures. As the temperature increases, the positive value of Δu decreases. Eugenol with Fluorobenzene mixtures show the highest positive Δu values among selected binary mixtures.

Weak intermolecular interaction are reported by negative Δu values and strong intermolecular interaction are indicated by positive Δu values [16, 17].

Due to strong intermolecular interaction between dissimilar molecules, molecules try to adjust tightly or closely to each other. In this situation, the sound wave can easily pass through the molecules and results in a high speed of sound (u) value. This higher value of speed of sound of the mixture than its pure compound values show the positive deviation in speed of sound (Δu).

Table-7 Isentropic Compressibility (k_s) and Deviation in Isentropic Compressibility (Δk_s) vs Mole Fraction (x_1) for Eugenol+ Fluoro-, Chloro- and Bromobenzene Mixtures at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15K.

x_1	k_s (TPa ⁻¹)			Δk_s (TPa ⁻¹)		
	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K
Eugenol (1) + Fluorobenzene (2)						
0.0000	753.82	785.82	819.76	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.0636	722.65	752.29	783.67	-11.54	-12.74	-13.97
0.1325	690.93	718.71	747.69	-21.98	-23.78	-25.97
0.2075	658.94	684.62	711.55	-30.81	-33.35	-36.02
0.2894	626.59	650.89	676.04	-37.87	-40.29	-43.02
0.3792	595.00	617.60	640.74	-41.72	-44.20	-47.07
0.4782	564.07	584.92	605.98	-42.10	-44.52	-47.40
0.5877	533.67	552.66	571.62	-38.68	-40.97	-43.66
0.7096	503.95	521.05	537.95	-30.76	-32.71	-34.91
0.8461	474.59	489.89	504.82	-17.97	-19.23	-20.54
1.0000	445.04	458.80	471.82	0.00	0.00	0.00
Eugenol (1) + Chlorobenzene (2)						
0.0000	585.75	606.22	627.71	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.0685	573.30	592.97	614.16	-2.82	-3.16	-2.87
0.1419	559.85	579.15	599.36	-5.93	-6.14	-6.22
0.2209	546.08	564.90	584.03	-8.59	-8.75	-9.24
0.3061	531.59	549.47	567.92	-11.09	-11.62	-12.08
0.3982	517.19	534.61	552.11	-12.53	-12.91	-13.52
0.4981	503.05	519.82	536.35	-12.62	-12.97	-13.71
0.6069	488.79	504.91	520.77	-11.57	-11.84	-12.33
0.7258	474.51	490.03	505.10	-9.11	-9.19	-9.47
0.8562	460.17	474.83	488.91	-5.11	-5.16	-5.32
1.0000	445.04	458.80	471.82	0.00	0.00	0.00
Eugenol (1) + Bromobenzene (2)						
0.0000	521.13	538.79	556.28	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.0705	515.29	532.49	550.04	-0.47	-0.66	-0.29
0.1458	508.04	525.26	542.26	-2.00	-1.87	-1.71
0.2264	500.29	517.22	533.84	-3.62	-3.47	-3.32
0.3128	492.47	509.02	524.86	-4.85	-4.75	-5.00
0.4057	484.66	500.56	516.01	-5.59	-5.78	-6.01
0.5060	476.93	492.43	507.49	-5.71	-5.89	-6.06
0.6144	469.26	484.50	499.01	-5.12	-5.15	-5.38
0.7320	461.78	476.54	490.73	-3.66	-3.70	-3.73
0.8600	453.82	468.22	481.93	-1.87	-1.78	-1.71
1.0000	445.04	458.80	471.82	0.00	0.00	0.00

Table-8 Fitting Coefficients (A_0, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4) with Standard Deviation (σ) for Least Square Representation of Δk_s for Eugenol + Fluoro-, Chloro- and Bromobenzene Mixtures at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K.

T (K)	A_0	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	σ
Fitting Coefficients (A_0, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4) for Δk_s						
Eugenol (1) + Fluorobenzene (2)						
303.15	-167.36500	42.54470	7.48715	-9.76249	-2.23502	7.56701
308.15	-176.97800	44.92780	0.77317	-5.25073	-2.23821	7.90591
313.15	-188.07600	47.17700	-7.88512	1.83694	3.68416	8.34299
Eugenol (1) + Chlorobenzene (2)						
303.15	-50.72980	7.98187	9.64068	-6.43032	3.60837	2.02473
308.15	-52.59430	9.31862	18.78930	-6.64954	-12.53370	2.08086
313.15	-54.82140	11.87000	15.10400	-12.98580	0.68838	2.24347

Eugenol (1) + Bromobenzene (2)						
303.15	-22.67790	5.50679	6.41931	-11.01560	15.22320	0.98700
308.15	-23.66310	4.21385	17.82070	-7.97097	-1.66222	1.02300
313.15	-24.50790	5.17562	17.91650	-11.94020	6.60897	1.12835

Figure - 3 Deviation in isentropic compressibility (Δk_s) for the system Eugenol (1) + Fluoro-, Chloro-, and Bromobenzene (2) as a function of mole fraction at $T = 303.15\text{K}$: ■, Eugenol (1) + Fluorobenzene (2); ●, Eugenol (1) + Chlorobenzene (2); ▲, Eugenol (1) + Bromobenzene (2).

All the binary mixtures indicate the negative values of Δk_s over the entire composition range at all studied temperatures. The Δk_s values change from negative to more negative values with increases of temperature. When the solvent is changed from fluorobenzene to bromobenzene, the negative values of Δk_s change from negative to less negative values [18,19].

Two unlike molecules i.e., halobenzene and eugenol are in close association and orientation with positive Δu values and negative Δk_s values. Both values are affected with an increase of temperature. Calculated data support for strong molecular interaction between eugenol and halobenzene.

Conclusion

In this work, we have measured density, and speed of sound for binary mixtures of Eugenol with three halobenzene like, fluorobenzene, chlorobenzene and bromobenzene at all studied temperatures. Excess molar volume, Deviation in speed of sound, and Deviation in isentropic compressibility are calculated and fitted with Redlich–Kister polynomials equations. The excess molar volume (V_m^E) values are negative for fluorobenzene and positive for chlorobenzene and bromobenzene in binary mixtures. However, the deviation in speed of sound showed a positive trend, and deviation in isentropic compressibility showed negative behavior for the binary systems under investigation indicating strong interactions between the components.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Department of Chemistry, Hemchandracharya North Gujarat University, Patan, for providing laboratory facilities from the Fluorobenzene, Chlorobenzene, and Bromobenzene binary mixtures.

References

- [1] Sumathi T, Uma Maheswari. 2009. *J. Indian J of Pure and Appl.Phys.*,47(11):782-786,2009.
- [2] Rama Rao GV, *Indian J of Pure and Appl. Phys.*, 42, 820-826,2004.
- [3] Narendra K. *e-Journal of Chem*, 7(3):927-934, 2010.
- [4] Ali A, Nain AK, *Ind. J. Pure & Appl. Phys.*,39, 421-427,2001.
- [5] Anwar. *Journal of the Chinese Chemical Society*, 51,477-485,2004.
- [6] S.M. Vilas-Boas, V. Pokorny, V. Stejfa, O. Ferreira, S.P. Pinho, K. Ruzicka, M. Fulem. Vapor pressure and thermophysical properties of eugenol and (+)-carvone, *Fluid Phase Equilib.* 499,112248,2019.
- [7] Milind P and Deepa K , Clove: A champion spices *Int. J. Res. Ayurveda Pharm.* 2 47–54, 2019.
- [8] Jentsch P V, Gualpa F, Ramos L A and Ciobota V, Adulteration of clove essential oil: Detection using a handheld raman spectrometer *Flavour Fragr. J.* 33 184–90, 2017.
- [9] Brendre R S, Rajput J D, Bagul S D and Karandikar P S, Outlooks on medicinal properties of eugenol and its synthetic derivatives *Nat. Prod. Chem. Res.* 4 2–6, 2016.
- [10] Atanasova-Pancevska N, Bogdanov J and Kungulovski D, Antimicrobial activity and chemical composition of two essential oils and eugenol from flower buds of *Eugenia caryophyllata* *Open Biol. Sci. J.* 3 16–25, 2017.
- [11] P. Bhanuprakash, C. Narasimha Rao, K. Sivakumar, (2016) Evaluation of molecular interactions by volumetric and acoustic studies in binary mixtures of the ionic liquid [EMIM][MeSO₄] with ethanoic and propanoic acid at different, *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 219: 79-87.
- [12] K. Sreenivasulu, V. Govinda, P. Venkateswarlu, K. Sivakumar, Thermodynamic properties of non electrolyte solutions, *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, 115,1805-1811,2014.
- [13] T. Kavitha, T. Vasantha, P. Venkatesu, R. S. Ramadevi, T. Hofman, Thermophysical properties for the mixed solvents of N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone with some of the imidazolium-based ionic liquids, *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 198, 11-20, 2014.
- [14] Nejad S M, Ozgüneş H and Başaran N, Pharmacological and toxicological properties of eugenol *Turk J. Pharm Sci.* 14, 2017.
- [15] Uddin M A, Shahinuzzaman M, Sohel Rana M and Yaakob Z , Study of chemical composition and medicinal properties of volatile oil from clove buds (*Eugenia caryophyllus*) *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Res.* 8, 895–899, 2017.
- [16] P.K. Pandey, A. Awasthi, A. Awasthi. Intermolecular interactions in binary mixtures of 2-chloroethanol with 2-dimethylaminoethanol and 2-diethylaminoethanol at different temperatures, *Chem. Phys.* 423, 119–126, 2013.
- [17] P. Patel, S. Sharma, Multifaceted analysis of intermolecular interactions in α -terpineol halobenzenes binary mixtures: Insights from thermophysical, acoustical, and spectral techniques, supported by quantum computational approaches, *Indian J. Chem.* 63, 1271–1293,2024.
- [18] Riddick, J. A., W. B. Bunger, and T. K. Sakano, "Organic Solvents: Techniques of Organic Chemistry." Vol. II. Wiley-Interscience, New York,1970.
- [19] Rusconi, Yvonne, *Physico-chemical constants of pure organic compounds* : J. Timmermans. Elsevier Publishing Company, Amsterdam, 693,1950.
- [20] J.N. Nayak, M.I. Aralaguppi, T.M. Aminabhavi, Density, viscosity, refractive index and speed of sound in the binary mixtures of ethyl chloroacetate + cyclohexanone, + chlorobenzene, + bromobenzene, or + benzyl Alcohol at (298.15, 303.15, and 308.15) K, *J. Chem. Eng. Data.* 48,628-63, 2003.
- [21] A.S. Al-Jimaz, J.A. Al-Kandary, A.H.M. Abdul-Latif, Acoustical and excess properties of (chlorobenzene + 1-hexanol, or 1-heptanol, or 1-octanol, or 1-nonanol, or 1-decanol) at (298.15, 303.15, 308.15, and 313.15) K, *J. Chem. Eng. Data.* 52,206–214,2007.
- [22] M. Gupta, D. Shukla, S. Parveen, S. Singh, J. Shukla, Mixing properties and modelling of methanol with chlorobenzene and bromobenzene at 293, 303, and 313 K, *Phys. Chem. Liq.* 47, 113–122,2009.
- [23] N.V. Sastry, R.R. Thakor, M.C. Patel. Thermophysical properties for diethylene glycol + nitrobenzene and triethylene glycol + (chloro-, bromo-, nitro-) benzene systems at different temperatures, *Int. J. Thermophys.* 29, 610-618, 2008.
- [24] M. Gupta, D. Shukla, S. Parveen, S. Singh, J. Shukla, Mixing properties and modelling of methanol with chlorobenzene and bromobenzene at 293, 303, and 313 K, *Phys. Chem. Liq.* 47, 113–122, 2009.
- [25] K.S. Reddy, Isentropic compressibilities of binary liquid mixtures at 303.15 and 313.15 K, *J. Chem. Eng. Data.* 31,238-240, 1986.